

Technical Appendix for: How Do Speaker Characteristics Influence Use of Rhetorical History?

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While conventional Topic Models only reflect the underlying text, the main advantage of STM is the latter's ability to incorporate the effects of metadata into its estimation of topics. As mentioned in the main text (section 3B), this allows us to directly test the hypothesis that speaker characteristics influence his or her rhetoric, including the usage of rhetorical history. In our model, frequency with which a topic is discussed is, therefore, defined as a function of the speaker's party affiliation, gender, age, educational attainment and Brexit stance, as well as the date variable, which records the day of the debate.¹ Next, a 15-topic STM is estimated based on the Brexit corpus presented in section 2.² Yet, how was this number of 15 topics defined? Recently, statisticians have introduced different metrics that can be used to compute the number of topics, but the resulting range of numbers only provides an indication of the optimal number of topics in a statistical sense. Social scientists, and particularly historians, agree that the specific research question should determine the number of topics and, therefore, simply test different models and compare them in terms of interpretability (cf. Wehrheim 2019; Ferri et al. 2018). We followed a similar trial-and-error process in this analysis, finally opting for a 15-topic model.

The final STM includes 15 topics, 6,720 documents, and a 16,075 word dictionary, with the estimated topics being displayed in the table below. The standard metric for characterising an estimated topic is plotting its highest probability words, which are based on the probabilities that each word is generated from each topic. Put simply: when discussing topic A in his or her speech, there is a high likelihood that politician B is using words listed in the word profile for topic A. Finding a group of words from topic A's word profile in one of the speeches, we can, therefore, use them as a proxy and conclude that this speech addresses, at least partly, topic A. In our case, we calculate for each topic not only those highest probability words, but also three additional types of word metrics (FREX, Lift, Score) that characterise the respective topic in a

¹ The variables are entered additively, and the date variable is allowed to have a non-linear relationship in the estimation stage.

² Using 'spectral initialization,' which means that, independent of the seed that is set, the same results will be generated.

certain statistical way.³ Combining these different word metrics leads to a more coherent and more easily interpretable word profile, which is why we recommend that other researchers use Topic Modeling to consider more metrics than the highest probability words when determining topic labels. After reading the word profiles, each consisting of four different word metrics, we attached a label to each topic.

Table 1. Topics Discovered Through Our Analysis

Topic	STM Output	Label
1	Highest Prob: people, bill, house, us, European, referendum, many FREX: democracy, voted, elected, voters, sovereignty, election, democratic Lift: —none, bring, democracy, desirable, enemy, God, ordinary Score: democracy, referendum, voted, people, sovereignty, election, conservative	<i>Democracy and Sovereignty</i>
2	Highest Prob: European, citizens, minister, union, EU, security, prime FREX: Munich, citizenship, foreign, security, warrant, arrest, citizens Lift: citizens, strong, adjective, agencies, ambivalent, Atlanta, attaches Score: citizenship, Munich, arrest, security, foreign, data, citizens	<i>Citizenship and Security</i>
3	Highest Prob: devolved, government, Scottish, Scotland, UK, powers, Wales FREX: JMC, Scotland's, devolution, frameworks, Scotland, administrations, devolved Lift: normally, SNP's, distant, tanks, deep, agricultural, devolve Score: Scottish, devolved, Scotland, administrations, devolution, Welsh, Wales	<i>Devolution</i>
4	Highest Prob: EU, UK, agreement, bill, exit, period, withdrawal FREX: implementation, period, transition, transitional, certainty, businesses, continue Lift: exit, ongoing, allow, cart, co-operation, contours, demonstrable Score: agreement, exit, implementation, UK, transitional, transition, negotiations	<i>Post-Brexit Transition</i>
5	Highest Prob: rights, children, EU, family, UK, equality, government FREX: children, children's, UNCRC, family, child, refugees, Euratom Lift: anti-trafficking, babies, Bowes, breastfeeding, dependants, experimental, FGM Score: children, child, children's, Euratom, rights, family, equality	<i>Family, Children and Refugees</i>
6	Highest Prob: environmental, EU, environment, government, standards, bill, public FREX: environmental, sentience, precautionary, watchdog, animal, environment, animals, pollution Lift: high, deserve, environmental, high, offer, pay, picks Score: environmental, animal, environment, watchdog, welfare, animals, sentience	<i>Environment</i>
7	Highest Prob: right, friend, clause, members, government, gentleman, new FREX: Rushcliffe, Beaconsfield, gentleman, east, constituents, Nottingham, Broxtowe Lift: -tank, ah, Beaconsfield, Beckett, Blomfield, bogged, contumacious Score: gentleman, Beaconsfield, clause, Rushcliffe, learned, constituents	<i>Parliamentary Rhetoric I</i>
8	Highest Prob: amendment, minister, government, learned, hope, friend, may FREX: helpful, moved, Mackay, points, learned, something, grateful Lift: shortly, sub-delegation, chilling, exhausted, fuzzy, helpful, non-devolved Score: learned, amendment, Mackay, Pannick, Clashfern, Wigley, friend	<i>Legal Rhetoric I</i>
9	Highest Prob: union, trade, market, customs, single, EU, European FREX: India, tariffs, customs, trade, single, free, tariff	<i>Trade</i>

³ FREX indicates words that are frequent and exclusive to each topic (Airoldi and Bischof 2016). Lift' weights words by dividing by their frequency in other topics, thereby prioritizing words that appear less frequently in other topics (Taddy 2013). Similar to lift, 'score' divides the log frequency of the word in the topic by the log frequency of the word in other topics.

	Lift: Allander, Australians, Barry, Brent, business, Canada-plus-plus-plus, catastrophe Score: customs, market, trade, EEA, tariffs, billion, India	
10	Highest Prob: parliament, government, deal, vote, house, amendment, bill FREX: meaningful, motion, mandate, vote, extension, date, notification Lift: neutral, dandelion, overt, rigidity, timed, duke, next Score: motion, vote, meaningful, grieve, article, parliament, agreement	<i>Parliamentary Rhetoric II</i>
11	Highest Prob: clause, act, EU, amendment, law, exit, day FREX: section, schedule, page, insert, provision, subsection, modify Lift: provisions, saving, EU-derived, including, primary, section a Score: retained, clause, schedule, insert, section, exit, paragraph	<i>Legal Rhetoric II</i>
12	Highest Prob: law, rights, EU, charter, court, courts, European FREX: charter, Francovich, damages, judges, courts, supreme, court Lift: disapply, ECHR, sex, see, general, allowed, another Score: charter, rights, law, retained, courts, court, human	<i>EU Law</i>
13	Highest Prob: Ireland, northern, border, agreement, good, Irish, Friday FREX: republic, border, Gibraltar, Irish, Friday, Ireland, northern Lift: normality, Browne, Ireland, Taoiseach, Trimble, island, agreement Score: Ireland, border, northern, Gibraltar, republic, Irish, Friday	<i>Irish Border</i>
14	Highest Prob: UK, EU, European, government, industry, research, Brexit FREX: trials, clinical, Erasmus, patients, medicines, funds, funding Lift: additionality, ageing, airlines, artists, attractions, audio-visual, Bangor Score: trials, clinical, Erasmus, funding, medicines, industry, patients	<i>Lack of Funding</i>
15	Highest Prob: powers, legislation, bill, committee, house, scrutiny, power FREX: affirmative, sifting, scrutiny, secondary, instruments, procedure, delegated Lift: affirmative, including, tax-like, among, appropriate, enemies, made Score: affirmative, powers, sifting, secondary, scrutiny, sis, delegated	<i>Parliamentary Rhetoric III</i>

According to the STM, the main topics discussed by British politicians surrounding Brexit were democracy and sovereignty; citizenship and security; devolution; post-Brexit transition; family, children and refugees; environment; trade; EU law; the Irish border; and post-Brexit lack of funding (e.g. medicine, education). In the following part, we will discuss the individual topics and explain the reasoning behind their respective labels. Usually, topics evoke specific associations, so that coherent labels can be inferred relatively quickly. Luckily, this was the case for most material in our sample, since our corpus was large enough to produce robust word profiles without obvious outliers. This effect might also be credited to the fact that, in contrast to most historical studies using Topic Modeling, we did not have to deal with Optical Character Recognition (OCR) errors (for this common problem, see: Romein et al. 2020), since the parliamentary debates on Brexit could be downloaded in a machine-readable format directly from the UK Government’s website, rather than having to be transformed from scans or pictures.⁴ However, it is worth re-emphasising that the labels were manually attached by the researchers and are, to a certain degree, subjective. Nevertheless, since the word profiles are

⁴ It is worth noting that topics are not always initially recognizable. If a topic lacks a straightforward interpretation, it is helpful to read the speeches that exhibit a large share of this topic in order to get a better sense of the proper interpretation of the word list and, therefore, the appropriate label. While this procedure was, strictly speaking, not necessary in the present case, it was followed for most topics listed in the table above as an additional robustness check.

automatically generated by the algorithm underlying the STM, it is hoped that the resulting topical structure of the debate is more objective than a mere cherry-picking of quotes related to a certain theme. With a large corpus consisting of thousands of speeches, employing machine learning tools like STM helps in structuring an otherwise difficult to comprehend mass of semantic data.

The first topic encompasses words such as ‘voters,’ ‘referendum,’ ‘democracy,’ and refers to concepts such as ‘sovereignty’ and ‘election.’ It has thus been labelled *Democracy and Sovereignty* (Topic 1). The existence of this topic can be seen as a reflection of the Brexit referendum campaign, during which much emphasis was placed by ‘Leave’ supporters on the lost parliamentary sovereignty, which could not be restored unless the UK exited the EU (Ringeyen-Biardeaud 2017). Next, words such as ‘citizenship,’ ‘citizens,’ ‘foreign,’ and ‘security’ refer to the discourse on *Citizenship and Security*, which is why Topic 2 has received this label. Noteworthy is the apparent inclusion of the ‘Chatham’ house rules and the annual ‘Munich’ security conference in the word profile. Coming to Topic 3, we encounter terms that deal with *Devolution* (‘devolved,’ ‘powers,’ ‘scotland,’ ‘wales,’ ‘administrations’). In England, devolution is the transfer of power and funding from national to local government. The impact of UK withdrawal from the EU on the UK’s devolution settlements is one of the most technically complex and politically contentious elements of the Brexit debate,⁵ so it makes sense that STM estimates a corresponding topic. The next topic deals with the *Post-Brexit Transition* (Topic 4) period and the settlement that would need to be negotiated with the EU during the one-year transition period. Topic 5 deals with the rights of *Family, Children and Refugees* in the light of Brexit. This topic refers to the legal situation of unaccompanied children stranded in Europe, who were reliant on EU rules to be legally and safely reunited with a family member in the UK.

Topic 6 deals with ‘pollution’ and ‘environmental’ ‘standards’ as well as the ‘welfare’ of ‘animals’ after Brexit and has thus been identified broadly as a discourse on the *Environment*. Topic 9 incorporates deliberations about *Trade* issues. It includes words such as ‘trade’, ‘single’ ‘European’ and ‘market’, but also ‘tariffs’ and ‘customs,’ thus referring to potential trade distortions that might occur after the transition period had ended. It also encompasses the countries with which British politicians aim to intensify trade relations in a post-Brexit world, such as ‘India,’ ‘Australia’ and “Canada“, thus reflecting the ‘Global Britain’ trading approach referred to by Theresa May. Likewise illuminating is Topic 12, which includes words like ‘law,’

⁵ For a summary, see: <https://publications.parliament.uk/pa/ld201719/ldselect/ldcom/9/903.htm> (31 August 2020).

‘EU,’ ‘charter,’ ‘supreme,’ ‘court,’ and ‘courts,’ thus referring to the field of *EU Law*. Removing the supremacy of EU law was a core element of the ‘Leave’ agenda, and the presence of this estimated topic implies that this concern was reflected in the parliamentary debates. Besides the terms listed above, the word profile for Topic 12 refers to the well-known *Francovich* decision of the European Court of Justice (ECJ) in 1991, which mandated that if a Government broke EU law then a claim in damages would lie if the breach had been sufficiently serious and had caused loss. The entry of ‘Francovich’ into the topic’s word profile, reflected the fact that the Withdrawal Bill would remove, with some very limited exceptions and a two-year grace period up to March 2021, any action for Francovich damages (Craig, 2019). According to the STM, the difficult question of the Irish Border (Topic 13) was also raised in the Brexit debates (‘ireland,’ ‘northern,’ ‘border’), alongside the question of Brexit’s impact on the Good Friday Agreement (‘agreement,’ ‘good,’ ‘Friday’). Finally, Topic 14 includes examples from the field of medicine (‘clinical,’ ‘trial,’ ‘patients,’ ‘medicines’) and R&D (‘research,’ ‘industry,’ ‘Erasmus’), reflecting concern that Brexit would precipitate a decline in funding, arising from inability to access certain EU funding schemes. This topic has, therefore, been labelled post-Brexit *Lack of Funding*.

Finally, in Topic Modeling studies the estimated topics do not necessarily have to describe a straightforward theme; they can form clusters of methodological words or even days of weeks (Wehrheim 2019). In our example, this happened for five topics, which feature many rhetorical terms that are either standard parliamentary language for starting/finishing one’s contribution to the debate (Topics 7, 10, 15) or denote legal terms that are related to the bill’s passage through the two Houses (Topics 8, 11). These terms were utilised by diverse speakers, irrespective of the particular theme discussed, and are, therefore, not very informative. These topics do not represent ‘errors’ on part of the model, but simply reflect the speeches’ occasion and might be ignored in our analysis. Note that the STM found all 15 topics without knowing that it deals with a set of political speeches and without any pre-coded definitions or lists of key terms that would bias the resulting selection of key topics.

As a robustness check, the quality of the estimated topics can be measured through a combination of their semantic coherence and exclusivity. Semantic coherence is maximised when the most probable words in a given topic frequently occur together (Mimno et al. 2011), whereas exclusivity of words to topics is included to ensure that high semantic coherence is not the result of a few topics being dominated by very common words. The figure below plots the semantic coherence and exclusivity scores for the 15 estimated topics. The results show that

the selected model features desirable properties in both dimensions and that many topics cluster towards the figure's upper right side.

Figure 2. Illustration of Semantic Coherence

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Topic 1:

Coefficients:

	Estimate	Std. Error	t value	Pr(> t)
(Intercept)	0.144996	0.251985	0.575	0.565029
partyCon/Deputy Speaker	0.301604	0.254811	1.184	0.236599
partyConservative	0.103094	0.100381	1.027	0.304442
partyDemocratic Unionist Party	0.137166	0.102940	1.332	0.182744
partyDep Speaker/Conservative	0.420344	0.251458	1.672	0.094645
partyDeputy Speaker	-0.130970	0.243612	-0.538	0.590861
partyGreen Party	0.112750	0.103312	1.091	0.275156
partyIndependent	0.058443	0.102046	0.573	0.566858
partyIndependent Labour	0.023363	0.175827	0.133	0.894298
partyLabour	0.116100	0.100306	1.157	0.247126
partyLabour/Deputy Speaker	0.443507	30.707183	0.014	0.988477
partyLiberal Democrat	0.130520	0.100607	1.297	0.194565
partyNon-affiliated	0.118013	0.100570	1.173	0.240662
partyPlaid Cymru	0.070285	0.101415	0.693	0.488310
partyScottish National Party	0.124229	0.100568	1.235	0.216773
partySpeaker	-0.141209	0.246455	-0.573	0.566691
partyUK Independence Party	0.219815	0.142930	1.538	0.124116
partyUlster Unionist	0.011432	0.106294	0.108	0.914358
stanceDid not vote	-0.284534	0.268015	-1.062	0.288440
stanceLaw Lord, probable Remain	-0.244469	0.233485	-1.047	0.295116
stanceLaw Lord, Unknown	-0.253008	0.270056	-0.937	0.348858
stanceLeave	-0.177828	0.228093	-0.780	0.435637
stanceNeutral	-0.007711	0.064833	-0.119	0.905335
stanceProbable Leave	-0.094296	0.275949	-0.342	0.732576
stanceProbable Remain	-0.236404	0.227614	-1.039	0.299021
stanceRemain	-0.225452	0.227146	-0.993	0.320968
stanceRemain/Neutral	-0.622138	30.707285	-0.020	0.983836
stanceSpeaker	-0.100819	0.120810	-0.835	0.404015
stanceThomas	-0.074412	0.305244	-0.244	0.807411
stanceUnknown	-0.256619	0.227362	-1.129	0.259073
stanceUnknown, although against 2nd ref	-0.053089	0.232779	-0.228	0.819603
genderMale	0.010801	0.005065	2.132	0.033015 *
s(date)1	0.274833	0.063031	4.360	1.32e-05 ***
s(date)2	0.019268	0.057527	0.335	0.737677
s(date)3	0.044514	0.040387	1.102	0.270421
s(date)4	0.012606	0.041575	0.303	0.761746
s(date)5	0.146337	0.041779	3.503	0.000464 ***
s(date)6	0.027595	0.041538	0.664	0.506511
s(date)7	-0.004927	0.040581	-0.121	0.903370
s(date)8	0.164736	0.068465	2.406	0.016149 *
s(date)9	0.211032	0.255976	0.824	0.409728
s(date)10	0.007415	0.041384	0.179	0.857805

Signif. codes: 0 '***' 0.001 '**' 0.01 '*' 0.05 '.' 0.1 ' ' 1

Topic 2:

Coefficients:

	Estimate	Std. Error	t value	Pr(> t)
(Intercept)	0.080024	0.168371	0.475	0.6346
partyCon/Deputy Speaker	0.080655	0.216869	0.372	0.7100
partyConservative	-0.037968	0.108435	-0.350	0.7262
partyDemocratic Unionist Party	-0.047677	0.110133	-0.433	0.6651
partyDep Speaker/Conservative	-0.056398	0.152597	-0.370	0.7117
partyDeputy Speaker	-0.003644	0.155571	-0.023	0.9813
partyGreen Party	-0.053934	0.108560	-0.497	0.6193
partyIndependent	-0.049900	0.109526	-0.456	0.6487
partyIndependent Labour	0.449359	0.255577	1.758	0.0788
partyLabour	-0.022167	0.108646	-0.204	0.8383
partyLabour/Deputy Speaker	0.064168	24.733197	0.003	0.9979
partyLiberal Democrat	0.007710	0.109174	0.071	0.9437
partyNon-affiliated	-0.021386	0.107112	-0.200	0.8418
partyPlaid Cymru	-0.025768	0.108969	-0.236	0.8131
partyScottish National Party	-0.021260	0.108871	-0.195	0.8452
partySpeaker	-0.021282	0.155838	-0.137	0.8914
partyUK Independence Party	0.042805	0.138377	0.309	0.7571
partyUlster Unionist	-0.050556	0.111362	-0.454	0.6499
stanceDid not vote	0.027325	0.162014	0.169	0.8661
stanceLaw Lord, probable Remain	0.206487	0.123633	1.670	0.0949
stanceLaw Lord, Unknown	0.414092	0.355848	1.164	0.2446
stanceLeave	0.033562	0.120614	0.278	0.7808
stanceNeutral	-0.002669	0.048280	-0.055	0.9559
stanceProbable Leave	0.010925	0.136556	0.080	0.9362
stanceProbable Remain	0.047344	0.120958	0.391	0.6955
stanceRemain	0.030098	0.120365	0.250	0.8026
stanceRemain/Neutral	-0.086210	24.733590	-0.003	0.9972
stanceSpeaker	0.248355	0.170766	1.454	0.1459
stanceThomas	-0.054804	0.162099	-0.338	0.7353
stanceUnknown	0.016871	0.120814	0.140	0.8889
stanceUnknown, although against 2nd ref	-0.025693	0.122729	-0.209	0.8342
genderMale	0.001056	0.003925	0.269	0.7879
s(date)1	-0.151018	0.058920	-2.563	0.0104 *
s(date)2	0.030043	0.047052	0.639	0.5232
s(date)3	-0.073248	0.040079	-1.828	0.0677 .
s(date)4	-0.065037	0.039817	-1.633	0.1024
s(date)5	-0.048672	0.041993	-1.159	0.2465
s(date)6	-0.047952	0.041071	-1.168	0.2430
s(date)7	-0.037821	0.039829	-0.950	0.3424
s(date)8	0.039159	0.059741	0.655	0.5122
s(date)9	-0.427093	0.197308	-2.165	0.0305 *
s(date)10	0.099579	0.041791	2.383	0.0172 *

Signif. codes: 0 '***' 0.001 '**' 0.01 '*' 0.05 '.' 0.1 ' ' 1

Topic 3:

Coefficients:

	Estimate	Std. Error	t value	Pr(> t)
(Intercept)	-0.105476	0.206176	-0.512	0.60896
partyCon/Deputy Speaker	-0.101112	0.186019	-0.544	0.58677
partyConservative	0.043795	0.109698	0.399	0.68974
partyDemocratic Unionist Party	-0.038568	0.113119	-0.341	0.73315
partyDep Speaker/Conservative	-0.076312	0.187634	-0.407	0.68424
partyDeputy Speaker	0.107516	0.187756	0.573	0.56691
partyGreen Party	0.037247	0.111492	0.334	0.73833
partyIndependent	0.038762	0.113539	0.341	0.73282
partyIndependent Labour	-0.074949	0.185703	-0.404	0.68652
partyLabour	0.032553	0.109646	0.297	0.76656
partyLabour/Deputy Speaker	0.325525	33.399745	0.010	0.99222
partyLiberal Democrat	0.062274	0.109771	0.567	0.57052
partyNon-affiliated	0.023791	0.110090	0.216	0.82891
partyPlaid Cymru	0.224578	0.110989	2.023	0.04307 *
partyScottish National Party	0.174625	0.110352	1.582	0.11360
partySpeaker	0.058844	0.188040	0.313	0.75434
partyUK Independence Party	-0.020206	0.125150	-0.161	0.87174
partyUlster Unionist	0.074452	0.123767	0.602	0.54749
stanceDid not vote	0.311734	0.327539	0.952	0.34126
stanceLaw Lord, probable Remain	0.088436	0.171860	0.515	0.60686
stanceLaw Lord, Unknown	0.088612	0.224842	0.394	0.69351
stanceLeave	0.070926	0.168845	0.420	0.67445
stanceNeutral	-0.026092	0.074085	-0.352	0.72471
stanceProbable Leave	0.227392	0.245608	0.926	0.35457
stanceProbable Remain	0.153083	0.169885	0.901	0.36757
stanceRemain	0.075423	0.168578	0.447	0.65460
stanceRemain/Neutral	-0.123866	33.401456	-0.004	0.99704
stanceSpeaker	-0.054248	0.132728	-0.409	0.68276
stanceThomas	0.051808	0.265708	0.195	0.84541
stanceUnknown	0.122722	0.169459	0.724	0.46897
stanceUnknown, although against 2nd ref	0.066195	0.172491	0.384	0.70117
genderMale	0.022996	0.005512	4.172	3.06e-05 ***
s(date)1	0.746069	0.068577	10.879	< 2e-16 ***
s(date)2	-1.007310	0.062621	-16.086	< 2e-16 ***
s(date)3	0.326649	0.044145	7.399	1.53e-13 ***
s(date)4	-0.240786	0.042364	-5.684	1.37e-08 ***
s(date)5	0.314727	0.045608	6.901	5.65e-12 ***
s(date)6	-0.112170	0.043238	-2.594	0.00950 **
s(date)7	0.113110	0.042233	2.678	0.00742 **
s(date)8	-0.466611	0.072585	-6.428	1.38e-10 ***
s(date)9	1.192673	0.250298	4.765	1.93e-06 ***
s(date)10	-0.036688	0.042265	-0.868	0.38541

Signif. codes: 0 '***' 0.001 '**' 0.01 '*' 0.05 '.' 0.1 ' ' 1

Topic 4:

Coefficients:

	Estimate	Std. Error	t value	Pr(> t)
(Intercept)	-0.021368	0.152006	-0.141	0.88821
partyCon/Deputy Speaker	0.048956	0.199142	0.246	0.80582
partyConservative	0.054141	0.081065	0.668	0.50424
partyDemocratic Unionist Party	-0.047159	0.082903	-0.569	0.56948
partyDep Speaker/Conservative	-0.098631	0.139063	-0.709	0.47819
partyDeputy Speaker	0.018562	0.140149	0.132	0.89463
partyGreen Party	-0.037463	0.082542	-0.454	0.64994
partyIndependent	-0.020317	0.082656	-0.246	0.80584
partyIndependent Labour	-0.012163	0.138539	-0.088	0.93005
partyLabour	0.013849	0.081047	0.171	0.86433
partyLabour/Deputy Speaker	0.595736	24.773184	0.024	0.98082
partyLiberal Democrat	0.010484	0.081216	0.129	0.89730
partyNon-affiliated	-0.008641	0.081346	-0.106	0.91541
partyPlaid Cymru	0.008269	0.082206	0.101	0.91988
partyScottish National Party	0.002694	0.081184	0.033	0.97353
partySpeaker	0.007054	0.140149	0.050	0.95986
partyUK Independence Party	-0.017191	0.093877	-0.183	0.85470
partyUlster Unionist	-0.041253	0.086425	-0.477	0.63314
stanceDid not vote	0.078819	0.198496	0.397	0.69132
stanceLaw Lord, probable Remain	0.020997	0.125242	0.168	0.86686
stanceLaw Lord, Unknown	-0.006139	0.166849	-0.037	0.97065
stanceLeave	0.049809	0.123703	0.403	0.68722
stanceNeutral	-0.003797	0.048868	-0.078	0.93806
stanceProbable Leave	-0.057423	0.140171	-0.410	0.68206
stanceProbable Remain	0.021619	0.123884	0.175	0.86147
stanceRemain	0.020541	0.123578	0.166	0.86799
stanceRemain/Neutral	-0.555612	24.772755	-0.022	0.98211
stanceSpeaker	0.033530	0.100803	0.333	0.73942
stanceThomas	-0.039304	0.165353	-0.238	0.81212
stanceUnknown	0.079090	0.123947	0.638	0.52343
stanceUnknown, although against 2nd ref	-0.027387	0.126262	-0.217	0.82829
genderMale	0.002337	0.004254	0.549	0.58270
s(date)1	-0.069315	0.049283	-1.406	0.15963
s(date)2	0.143489	0.041957	3.420	0.00063 ***
s(date)3	0.003834	0.031795	0.121	0.90403
s(date)4	0.032894	0.032171	1.022	0.30661
s(date)5	0.005122	0.033631	0.152	0.87894
s(date)6	0.010910	0.032258	0.338	0.73522
s(date)7	0.053411	0.032178	1.660	0.09699 .
s(date)8	0.024222	0.059039	0.410	0.68162
s(date)9	-0.208834	0.221665	-0.942	0.34617
s(date)10	0.036319	0.031871	1.140	0.25451

Signif. codes: 0 '***' 0.001 '**' 0.01 '*' 0.05 '.' 0.1 ' ' 1

Topic 5:

Coefficients:

	Estimate	Std. Error	t value	Pr(> t)
(Intercept)	-0.011485	0.156763	-0.073	0.941600
partyCon/Deputy Speaker	-0.018891	0.147779	-0.128	0.898284
partyConservative	0.015506	0.082757	0.187	0.851376
partyDemocratic Unionist Party	0.009984	0.084284	0.118	0.905706
partyDep Speaker/Conservative	-0.003218	0.140200	-0.023	0.981690
partyDeputy Speaker	0.033912	0.143295	0.237	0.812927
partyGreen Party	-0.031938	0.084555	-0.378	0.705650
partyIndependent	0.026648	0.086246	0.309	0.757352
partyIndependent Labour	0.033896	0.162479	0.209	0.834754
partyLabour	0.038783	0.082987	0.467	0.640273
partyLabour/Deputy Speaker	0.249251	25.318058	0.010	0.992145
partyLiberal Democrat	0.010980	0.083062	0.132	0.894836
partyNon-affiliated	0.033873	0.082951	0.408	0.683027
partyPlaid Cymru	0.016178	0.083528	0.194	0.846426
partyScottish National Party	0.029342	0.083358	0.352	0.724846
partySpeaker	0.053638	0.143248	0.374	0.708090
partyUK Independence Party	-0.006652	0.094869	-0.070	0.944099
partyUlster Unionist	-0.009017	0.087574	-0.103	0.917992
stanceDid not vote	0.011741	0.167850	0.070	0.944236
stanceLaw Lord, probable Remain	0.016251	0.126829	0.128	0.898048
stanceLaw Lord, Unknown	-0.005182	0.167958	-0.031	0.975386
stanceLeave	0.059214	0.125512	0.472	0.637100
stanceNeutral	0.018516	0.049944	0.371	0.710842
stanceProbable Leave	0.041518	0.142185	0.292	0.770294
stanceProbable Remain	0.021993	0.125792	0.175	0.861214
stanceRemain	0.058609	0.125303	0.468	0.639986
stanceRemain/Neutral	-0.228389	25.318946	-0.009	0.992803
stanceSpeaker	0.021093	0.096691	0.218	0.827321
stanceThomas	0.056881	0.168519	0.338	0.735722
stanceUnknown	0.050864	0.125732	0.405	0.685827
stanceUnknown, although against 2nd ref	0.033004	0.128380	0.257	0.797126
genderMale	-0.041102	0.004091	-10.048	< 2e-16 ***
s(date)1	-0.088486	0.057454	-1.540	0.123578
s(date)2	0.049982	0.045616	1.096	0.273249
s(date)3	-0.023715	0.038832	-0.611	0.541423
s(date)4	-0.003600	0.038889	-0.093	0.926237
s(date)5	-0.063983	0.040270	-1.589	0.112141
s(date)6	0.082381	0.039010	2.112	0.034741 *
s(date)7	-0.038937	0.038577	-1.009	0.312853
s(date)8	0.257057	0.067584	3.804	0.000144 ***
s(date)9	-0.848637	0.228512	-3.714	0.000206 ***
s(date)10	0.011524	0.037794	0.305	0.760446

Signif. codes: 0 '***' 0.001 '**' 0.01 '*' 0.05 '.' 0.1 ' ' 1

Topic 6:

Coefficients:

	Estimate	Std. Error	t value	Pr(> t)
(Intercept)	-0.0580191	0.1714254	-0.338	0.73503
partyCon/Deputy Speaker	-0.0193348	0.1547354	-0.125	0.90056
partyConservative	0.0274588	0.0902602	0.304	0.76097
partyDemocratic Unionist Party	0.0196020	0.0925841	0.212	0.83233
partyDep Speaker/Conservative	0.0195801	0.1543724	0.127	0.89907
partyDeputy Speaker	0.0298941	0.1581021	0.189	0.85004
partyGreen Party	0.3054698	0.0960580	3.180	0.00148 **
partyIndependent	-0.0146843	0.0929628	-0.158	0.87449
partyIndependent Labour	0.0477279	0.1695550	0.281	0.77834
partyLabour	0.0384980	0.0903825	0.426	0.67016
partyLabour/Deputy Speaker	-0.1847629	27.9353799	-0.007	0.99472
partyLiberal Democrat	0.0235984	0.0905278	0.261	0.79435
partyNon-affiliated	0.0317509	0.0904658	0.351	0.72562
partyPlaid Cymru	0.0314704	0.0912745	0.345	0.73026
partyScottish National Party	0.0044395	0.0906298	0.049	0.96093
partySpeaker	0.0293803	0.1574547	0.187	0.85198
partyUK Independence Party	-0.0046231	0.1032780	-0.045	0.96430
partyUlster Unionist	0.0242685	0.0971267	0.250	0.80270
stanceDid not vote	0.0077195	0.1875193	0.041	0.96716
stanceLaw Lord, probable Remain	0.0243247	0.1415253	0.172	0.86354
stanceLaw Lord, Unknown	-0.0020770	0.1874370	-0.011	0.99116
stanceLeave	0.0576998	0.1398972	0.412	0.68003
stanceNeutral	0.0317070	0.0551265	0.575	0.56520
stanceProbable Leave	0.0323014	0.1571658	0.206	0.83717
stanceProbable Remain	0.0434260	0.1403441	0.309	0.75701
stanceRemain	0.0588395	0.1397918	0.421	0.67384
stanceRemain/Neutral	0.2417991	27.9377276	0.009	0.99309
stanceSpeaker	0.1355512	0.1612807	0.840	0.40068
stanceThomas	0.0427136	0.1893891	0.226	0.82157
stanceUnknown	0.0407672	0.1402168	0.291	0.77126
stanceUnknown, although against 2nd ref	0.0003904	0.1429297	0.003	0.99782
genderMale	-0.0383400	0.0051879	-7.390	1.64e-13 ***
s(date)1	-0.0757865	0.0544719	-1.391	0.16418
s(date)2	0.2297574	0.0472941	4.858	1.21e-06 ***
s(date)3	0.0050882	0.0351958	0.145	0.88505
s(date)4	0.0664607	0.0355044	1.872	0.06126 .
s(date)5	-0.0100816	0.0383674	-0.263	0.79274
s(date)6	0.0887042	0.0359045	2.471	0.01351 *
s(date)7	0.0099107	0.0352816	0.281	0.77879
s(date)8	0.2639770	0.0610353	4.325	1.55e-05 ***
s(date)9	-0.6324686	0.2294440	-2.757	0.00586 **
s(date)10	0.0378249	0.0356067	1.062	0.28814

 Signif. codes: 0 '***' 0.001 '**' 0.01 '*' 0.05 '.' 0.1 ' ' 1

Topic 7:

Coefficients:

	Estimate	Std. Error	t value	Pr(> t)
(Intercept)	0.381352	0.198304	1.923	0.054514 .
partyCon/Deputy Speaker	0.009598	0.164913	0.058	0.953592
partyConservative	0.027470	0.094962	0.289	0.772381
partyDemocratic Unionist Party	0.062016	0.099454	0.624	0.532938
partyDep Speaker/Conservative	0.032057	0.164212	0.195	0.845226
partyDeputy Speaker	0.335394	0.168436	1.991	0.046497 *
partyGreen Party	0.031194	0.098429	0.317	0.751315
partyIndependent	0.015401	0.099872	0.154	0.877453
partyIndependent Labour	-0.044661	0.164707	-0.271	0.786283
partyLabour	0.017894	0.094880	0.189	0.850412
partyLabour/Deputy Speaker	-0.052308	29.339262	-0.002	0.998578
partyLiberal Democrat	0.022951	0.095130	0.241	0.809360
partyNon-affiliated	0.015726	0.095014	0.166	0.868545
partyPlaid Cymru	-0.016114	0.095526	-0.169	0.866049
partyScottish National Party	0.001981	0.095325	0.021	0.983424
partySpeaker	0.459662	0.171968	2.673	0.007537 **
partyUK Independence Party	-0.017368	0.108893	-0.159	0.873281
partyUlster Unionist	-0.001870	0.100980	-0.019	0.985227
stanceDid not vote	-0.169247	0.234995	-0.720	0.471417
stanceLaw Lord, probable Remain	-0.077336	0.164432	-0.470	0.638139
stanceLaw Lord, Unknown	-0.074506	0.208995	-0.356	0.721479
stanceLeave	-0.073359	0.162280	-0.452	0.651246
stanceNeutral	-0.126970	0.090679	-1.400	0.161493
stanceProbable Leave	0.032818	0.199299	0.165	0.869211
stanceProbable Remain	-0.076214	0.162807	-0.468	0.639710
stanceRemain	-0.075066	0.162725	-0.461	0.644592
stanceRemain/Neutral	0.252634	29.338237	0.009	0.993130
stanceSpeaker	-0.589661	0.147248	-4.005	6.28e-05 ***
stanceThomas	-0.093824	0.211370	-0.444	0.657141
stanceUnknown	-0.089075	0.162592	-0.548	0.583818
stanceUnknown, although against 2nd ref	-0.075974	0.165605	-0.459	0.646415
genderMale	0.015204	0.004922	3.089	0.002018 **
s(date)1	-0.183902	0.082796	-2.221	0.026375 *
s(date)2	-0.030257	0.060334	-0.501	0.616042
s(date)3	-0.206143	0.054145	-3.807	0.000142 ***
s(date)4	-0.086580	0.054075	-1.601	0.109396
s(date)5	-0.239374	0.055673	-4.300	1.74e-05 ***
s(date)6	-0.377624	0.054891	-6.880	6.55e-12 ***
s(date)7	-0.315238	0.054130	-5.824	6.02e-09 ***
s(date)8	-0.419873	0.071644	-5.861	4.83e-09 ***
s(date)9	-0.052458	0.213229	-0.246	0.805677
s(date)10	-0.340121	0.054313	-6.262	4.03e-10 ***

Signif. codes: 0 '***' 0.001 '**' 0.01 '*' 0.05 '.' 0.1 ' ' 1

Topic 8:

Coefficients:

	Estimate	Std. Error	t value	Pr(> t)
(Intercept)	0.070199	0.247467	0.284	0.77667
partyCon/Deputy Speaker	-0.082273	0.236992	-0.347	0.72849
partyConservative	-0.034842	0.166506	-0.209	0.83426
partyDemocratic Unionist Party	-0.010952	0.169464	-0.065	0.94847
partyDep Speaker/Conservative	-0.004723	0.283756	-0.017	0.98672
partyDeputy Speaker	0.081748	0.236682	0.345	0.72981
partyGreen Party	-0.058057	0.167386	-0.347	0.72872
partyIndependent	-0.060775	0.166936	-0.364	0.71582
partyIndependent Labour	-0.194326	0.221962	-0.875	0.38134
partyLabour	-0.083155	0.165854	-0.501	0.61612
partyLabour/Deputy Speaker	-0.065338	33.981764	-0.002	0.99847
partyLiberal Democrat	-0.097921	0.166808	-0.587	0.55721
partyNon-affiliated	-0.065631	0.166420	-0.394	0.69332
partyPlaid Cymru	-0.069963	0.168504	-0.415	0.67801
partyScottish National Party	-0.084531	0.166281	-0.508	0.61122
partySpeaker	0.140506	0.235280	0.597	0.55040
partyUK Independence Party	-0.158433	0.178228	-0.889	0.37407
partyUlster Unionist	-0.027466	0.169423	-0.162	0.87122
stanceDid not vote	0.005415	0.228218	0.024	0.98107
stanceLaw Lord, probable Remain	0.059797	0.172243	0.347	0.72848
stanceLaw Lord, Unknown	-0.124144	0.227619	-0.545	0.58550
stanceLeave	0.025538	0.171271	0.149	0.88147
stanceNeutral	0.007410	0.070888	0.105	0.91675
stanceProbable Leave	-0.049115	0.193037	-0.254	0.79917
stanceProbable Remain	0.092757	0.171190	0.542	0.58795
stanceRemain	0.092334	0.170759	0.541	0.58872
stanceRemain/Neutral	0.010420	33.979096	0.000	0.99976
stanceSpeaker	-0.202505	0.135563	-1.494	0.13527
stanceThomas	0.136022	0.295343	0.461	0.64513
stanceUnknown	0.098081	0.171103	0.573	0.56651
stanceUnknown, although against 2nd ref	0.044994	0.177177	0.254	0.79954
genderMale	0.024261	0.005308	4.571	4.95e-06 ***
s(date)1	-0.333349	0.066633	-5.003	5.80e-07 ***
s(date)2	0.147582	0.060514	2.439	0.01476 *
s(date)3	-0.066878	0.044605	-1.499	0.13383
s(date)4	0.027777	0.046294	0.600	0.54852
s(date)5	-0.113463	0.046458	-2.442	0.01462 *
s(date)6	0.142954	0.048575	2.943	0.00326 **
s(date)7	0.119213	0.045183	2.638	0.00835 **
s(date)8	0.070324	0.080348	0.875	0.38147
s(date)9	-0.127409	0.297775	-0.428	0.66876
s(date)10	0.065303	0.045353	1.440	0.14995

Signif. codes: 0 '***' 0.001 '**' 0.01 '*' 0.05 '.' 0.1 ' ' 1

Topic 9:

Coefficients:

	Estimate	Std. Error	t value	Pr(> t)
(Intercept)	0.0670090	0.2642599	0.254	0.799834
partyCon/Deputy Speaker	0.1291975	0.2425284	0.533	0.594251
partyConservative	-0.0098968	0.1088347	-0.091	0.927548
partyDemocratic Unionist Party	0.0226373	0.1111201	0.204	0.838579
partyDep Speaker/Conservative	0.0020550	0.1836209	0.011	0.991071
partyDeputy Speaker	-0.1368150	0.2524056	-0.542	0.587806
partyGreen Party	-0.0003935	0.1107143	-0.004	0.997164
partyIndependent	-0.0532956	0.1111236	-0.480	0.631523
partyIndependent Labour	0.1464553	0.2521202	0.581	0.561331
partyLabour	0.0440612	0.1088140	0.405	0.685548
partyLabour/Deputy Speaker	-0.1537933	33.0343682	-0.005	0.996286
partyLiberal Democrat	0.0287490	0.1092445	0.263	0.792434
partyNon-affiliated	0.0010579	0.1091368	0.010	0.992266
partyPlaid Cymru	0.0210960	0.1089510	0.194	0.846473
partyScottish National Party	0.0373513	0.1097667	0.340	0.733657
partySpeaker	-0.1689674	0.2512405	-0.673	0.501268
partyUK Independence Party	0.2681889	0.1386669	1.934	0.053149
partyUlster Unionist	0.0680297	0.1175935	0.579	0.562936
stanceDid not vote	0.1011604	0.3426488	0.295	0.767827
stanceLaw Lord, probable Remain	0.0186335	0.2428371	0.077	0.938839
stanceLaw Lord, Unknown	0.1130166	0.3122445	0.362	0.717402
stanceLeave	-0.0541728	0.2410413	-0.225	0.822185
stanceNeutral	0.0322780	0.0628616	0.513	0.607635
stanceProbable Leave	-0.1091831	0.2558758	-0.427	0.669609
stanceProbable Remain	-0.0803811	0.2426372	-0.331	0.740443
stanceRemain	-0.0714016	0.2407729	-0.297	0.766818
stanceRemain/Neutral	0.0119804	33.0369869	0.000	0.999711
stanceSpeaker	0.0137385	0.1256364	0.109	0.912927
stanceThomas	0.0961027	0.3583380	0.268	0.788561
stanceUnknown	-0.0966594	0.2417956	-0.400	0.689349
stanceUnknown, although against 2nd ref	-0.0983080	0.2361931	-0.416	0.677263
genderMale	0.0103625	0.0050857	2.038	0.041634 *
s(date)1	-0.0112049	0.0653929	-0.171	0.863956
s(date)2	0.1375944	0.0605679	2.272	0.023134 *
s(date)3	0.0044586	0.0413196	0.108	0.914075
s(date)4	0.1590807	0.0430090	3.699	0.000218 ***
s(date)5	0.0281349	0.0435347	0.646	0.518131
s(date)6	0.0937704	0.0424512	2.209	0.027215 *
s(date)7	-0.0220657	0.0411358	-0.536	0.591692
s(date)8	0.2985545	0.0709354	4.209	2.60e-05 ***
s(date)9	-1.0112494	0.2596234	-3.895	9.91e-05 ***
s(date)10	0.0158896	0.0412913	0.385	0.700385

Signif. codes: 0 '***' 0.001 '**' 0.01 '*' 0.05 '.' 0.1 ' ' 1

Topic 10:

Coefficients:

	Estimate	Std. Error	t value	Pr(> t)	
(Intercept)	0.188170	0.278446	0.676	0.49920	
partyCon/Deputy Speaker	0.214140	0.187430	1.143	0.25328	
partyConservative	0.151212	0.105872	1.428	0.15326	
partyDemocratic Unionist Party	0.171681	0.108651	1.580	0.11413	
partyDep Speaker/Conservative	0.138075	0.179788	0.768	0.44252	
partyDeputy Speaker	-0.095491	0.265849	-0.359	0.71946	
partyGreen Party	0.132360	0.108215	1.223	0.22133	
partyIndependent	0.096187	0.108541	0.886	0.37555	
partyIndependent Labour	0.101998	0.182460	0.559	0.57617	
partyLabour	0.172525	0.105931	1.629	0.10343	
partyLabour/Deputy Speaker	-0.388609	32.357784	-0.012	0.99042	
partyLiberal Democrat	0.148854	0.106056	1.404	0.16050	
partyNon-affiliated	0.138781	0.106036	1.309	0.19064	
partyPlaid Cymru	0.163165	0.107077	1.524	0.12760	
partyScottish National Party	0.128524	0.106141	1.211	0.22598	
partySpeaker	-0.118285	0.266445	-0.444	0.65710	
partyUK Independence Party	0.113825	0.126315	0.901	0.36755	
partyUlster Unionist	0.124538	0.113946	1.093	0.27446	
stanceDid not vote	-0.222921	0.289156	-0.771	0.44077	
stanceLaw Lord, probable Remain	-0.127620	0.248872	-0.513	0.60811	
stanceLaw Lord, Unknown	-0.309260	0.288950	-1.070	0.28453	
stanceLeave	-0.189542	0.247626	-0.765	0.44404	
stanceNeutral	0.016050	0.063903	0.251	0.80169	
stanceProbable Leave	-0.003561	0.278015	-0.013	0.98978	
stanceProbable Remain	-0.145092	0.247028	-0.587	0.55699	
stanceRemain	-0.185152	0.247253	-0.749	0.45398	
stanceRemain/Neutral	0.274184	32.355729	0.008	0.99324	
stanceSpeaker	0.005162	0.125355	0.041	0.96716	
stanceThomas	-0.260207	0.288822	-0.901	0.36766	
stanceUnknown	-0.239449	0.248035	-0.965	0.33439	
stanceUnknown, although against 2nd ref	0.005958	0.259372	0.023	0.98168	
genderMale	0.017631	0.005463	3.227	0.00126	**
s(date)1	-0.296720	0.092191	-3.219	0.00129	**
s(date)2	0.103046	0.064301	1.603	0.10908	
s(date)3	-0.176039	0.060745	-2.898	0.00377	**
s(date)4	0.023435	0.057973	0.404	0.68605	
s(date)5	-0.151370	0.063344	-2.390	0.01689	*
s(date)6	-0.114210	0.059232	-1.928	0.05388	.
s(date)7	-0.096412	0.059593	-1.618	0.10575	
s(date)8	-0.055609	0.084552	-0.658	0.51076	
s(date)9	1.396178	0.319952	4.364	1.3e-05	***
s(date)10	-0.164805	0.058169	-2.833	0.00462	**

Signif. codes: 0 '***' 0.001 '**' 0.01 '*' 0.05 '.' 0.1 ' ' 1

Topic 11:

Coefficients:

	Estimate	Std. Error	t value	Pr(> t)
(Intercept)	-0.076417	0.140289	-0.545	0.58597
partyCon/Deputy Speaker	-0.050992	0.120893	-0.422	0.67319
partyConservative	0.006656	0.073604	0.090	0.92795
partyDemocratic Unionist Party	-0.007607	0.074645	-0.102	0.91883
partyDep Speaker/Conservative	0.263209	0.251267	1.048	0.29489
partyDeputy Speaker	0.150275	0.122153	1.230	0.21866
partyGreen Party	0.009478	0.076247	0.124	0.90108
partyIndependent	0.069229	0.078045	0.887	0.37508
partyIndependent Labour	-0.023378	0.120464	-0.194	0.84613
partyLabour	-0.003508	0.073515	-0.048	0.96194
partyLabour/Deputy Speaker	0.012727	20.961809	0.001	0.99952
partyLiberal Democrat	0.012364	0.073692	0.168	0.86677
partyNon-affiliated	0.024570	0.073151	0.336	0.73697
partyPlaid Cymru	-0.014015	0.074286	-0.189	0.85037
partyScottish National Party	-0.012316	0.073951	-0.167	0.86773
partySpeaker	0.054921	0.122532	0.448	0.65401
partyUK Independence Party	0.005940	0.084159	0.071	0.94374
partyUlster Unionist	-0.002422	0.080797	-0.030	0.97608
stanceDid not vote	0.029816	0.152193	0.196	0.84469
stanceLaw Lord, probable Remain	0.019328	0.115715	0.167	0.86735
stanceLaw Lord, Unknown	-0.017199	0.149626	-0.115	0.90849
stanceLeave	0.036191	0.115120	0.314	0.75325
stanceNeutral	0.022729	0.064255	0.354	0.72355
stanceProbable Leave	0.003262	0.127643	0.026	0.97962
stanceProbable Remain	0.039470	0.115437	0.342	0.73242
stanceRemain	0.042048	0.114764	0.366	0.71409
stanceRemain/Neutral	0.306926	20.960235	0.015	0.98832
stanceSpeaker	0.329806	0.167815	1.965	0.04942 *
stanceThomas	-0.019798	0.149784	-0.132	0.89485
stanceUnknown	0.074374	0.114493	0.650	0.51598
stanceUnknown, although against 2nd ref	0.038510	0.118433	0.325	0.74507
genderMale	0.005367	0.003658	1.467	0.14245
s(date)1	0.020413	0.051187	0.399	0.69005
s(date)2	0.147215	0.041327	3.562	0.00037 ***
s(date)3	0.045210	0.034665	1.304	0.19221
s(date)4	0.091327	0.034099	2.678	0.00742 **
s(date)5	0.011211	0.035829	0.313	0.75436
s(date)6	0.092495	0.034769	2.660	0.00783 **
s(date)7	0.078771	0.034233	2.301	0.02142 *
s(date)8	0.060870	0.053452	1.139	0.25484
s(date)9	-0.229272	0.166496	-1.377	0.16854
s(date)10	0.052679	0.034055	1.547	0.12194

 Signif. codes: 0 '***' 0.001 '**' 0.01 '*' 0.05 '.' 0.1 ' ' 1

Topic 12:

Coefficients:

	Estimate	Std. Error	t value	Pr(> t)
(Intercept)	0.027570	0.228919	0.120	0.90414
partyCon/Deputy Speaker	-0.081477	0.196047	-0.416	0.67772
partyConservative	0.064865	0.114979	0.564	0.57267
partyDemocratic Unionist Party	0.022892	0.118256	0.194	0.84651
partyDep Speaker/Conservative	-0.052226	0.197766	-0.264	0.79173
partyDeputy Speaker	0.007627	0.212926	0.036	0.97143
partyGreen Party	0.065363	0.118380	0.552	0.58087
partyIndependent	0.113245	0.119944	0.944	0.34513
partyIndependent Labour	-0.011664	0.200133	-0.058	0.95353
partyLabour	0.044023	0.115047	0.383	0.70199
partyLabour/Deputy Speaker	0.515762	36.147867	0.014	0.98862
partyLiberal Democrat	0.046214	0.115458	0.400	0.68897
partyNon-affiliated	0.101792	0.115789	0.879	0.37937
partyPlaid Cymru	0.011364	0.116243	0.098	0.92212
partyScottish National Party	0.046977	0.115945	0.405	0.68537
partySpeaker	0.072528	0.211536	0.343	0.73171
partyUK Independence Party	0.023846	0.133856	0.178	0.85862
partyUlster Unionist	0.004877	0.121725	0.040	0.96804
stanceDid not vote	-0.077755	0.245817	-0.316	0.75178
stanceLaw Lord, probable Remain	-0.095050	0.187278	-0.508	0.61180
stanceLaw Lord, Unknown	-0.097036	0.242902	-0.399	0.68955
stanceLeave	-0.004345	0.185695	-0.023	0.98133
stanceNeutral	-0.037649	0.068392	-0.550	0.58200
stanceProbable Leave	-0.070222	0.207077	-0.339	0.73454
stanceProbable Remain	-0.042600	0.186436	-0.228	0.81927
stanceRemain	0.006150	0.185724	0.033	0.97359
stanceRemain/Neutral	-0.509334	36.147912	-0.014	0.98876
stanceSpeaker	0.128325	0.171977	0.746	0.45559
stanceThomas	-0.019114	0.246805	-0.077	0.93827
stanceUnknown	0.063516	0.185345	0.343	0.73184
stanceUnknown, although against 2nd ref	0.010883	0.190302	0.057	0.95440
genderMale	-0.006421	0.006357	-1.010	0.31249
s(date)1	-0.218048	0.070813	-3.079	0.00208 **
s(date)2	0.284356	0.061531	4.621	3.88e-06 ***
s(date)3	0.024152	0.046721	0.517	0.60521
s(date)4	-0.118319	0.047024	-2.516	0.01189 *
s(date)5	0.011560	0.048806	0.237	0.81278
s(date)6	0.029155	0.047395	0.615	0.53848
s(date)7	-0.066490	0.045790	-1.452	0.14653
s(date)8	0.109637	0.076313	1.437	0.15086
s(date)9	-0.526958	0.274697	-1.918	0.05511 .
s(date)10	0.077712	0.047628	1.632	0.10280

 Signif. codes: 0 '***' 0.001 '**' 0.01 '*' 0.05 '.' 0.1 ' ' 1

Topic 13:

Coefficients:

	Estimate	Std. Error	t value	Pr(> t)
(Intercept)	0.4307556	0.2687194	1.603	0.10898
partyCon/Deputy Speaker	-0.5412146	0.2508600	-2.157	0.03101 *
partyConservative	-0.4946642	0.2198422	-2.250	0.02448 *
partyDemocratic Unionist Party	-0.3043132	0.2262305	-1.345	0.17862
partyDep Speaker/Conservative	-0.5265591	0.2497397	-2.108	0.03503 *
partyDeputy Speaker	-0.4704408	0.2629535	-1.789	0.07365 .
partyGreen Party	-0.5106028	0.2201145	-2.320	0.02039 *
partyIndependent	-0.2068480	0.2209805	-0.936	0.34928
partyIndependent Labour	-0.5515251	0.2547934	-2.165	0.03045 *
partyLabour	-0.4852499	0.2200209	-2.205	0.02745 *
partyLabour/Deputy Speaker	-0.5968123	27.0147736	-0.022	0.98238
partyLiberal Democrat	-0.5030809	0.2203446	-2.283	0.02245 *
partyNon-affiliated	-0.5012681	0.2188296	-2.291	0.02201 *
partyPlaid Cymru	-0.4806650	0.2189031	-2.196	0.02814 *
partyScottish National Party	-0.5019097	0.2205120	-2.276	0.02287 *
partySpeaker	-0.4980507	0.2616615	-1.903	0.05703 .
partyUK Independence Party	-0.5181316	0.2272636	-2.280	0.02265 *
partyUlster Unionist	-0.1650085	0.2388908	-0.691	0.48976
stanceDid not vote	0.0006465	0.1879940	0.003	0.99726
stanceLaw Lord, probable Remain	0.0984893	0.1466660	0.672	0.50191
stanceLaw Lord, Unknown	0.0481433	0.1898628	0.254	0.79984
stanceLeave	0.0531021	0.1449807	0.366	0.71418
stanceNeutral	0.0351719	0.0520630	0.676	0.49934
stanceProbable Leave	0.0105919	0.1613783	0.066	0.94767
stanceProbable Remain	0.0593795	0.1454704	0.408	0.68315
stanceRemain	0.0668011	0.1446409	0.462	0.64421
stanceRemain/Neutral	0.1581573	27.0190261	0.006	0.99533
stanceSpeaker	0.0151011	0.1026132	0.147	0.88301
stanceThomas	0.0289417	0.1869541	0.155	0.87698
stanceUnknown	0.0469852	0.1451807	0.324	0.74623
stanceUnknown, although against 2nd ref	0.0224952	0.1475124	0.152	0.87880
genderMale	0.0018505	0.0045010	0.411	0.68099
s(date)1	0.2121040	0.0531184	3.993	6.59e-05 ***
s(date)2	-0.3124429	0.0471118	-6.632	3.57e-11 ***
s(date)3	0.1114527	0.0344934	3.231	0.00124 **
s(date)4	-0.0403895	0.0342488	-1.179	0.23832
s(date)5	0.1064087	0.0361892	2.940	0.00329 **
s(date)6	0.0474885	0.0345031	1.376	0.16876
s(date)7	0.0487487	0.0340387	1.432	0.15215
s(date)8	-0.0799036	0.0598793	-1.334	0.18211
s(date)9	0.4288869	0.2216588	1.935	0.05305 .
s(date)10	0.0111448	0.0339727	0.328	0.74288

 Signif. codes: 0 '***' 0.001 '**' 0.01 '*' 0.05 '.' 0.1 ' ' 1

Topic 14:

Coefficients:

	Estimate	Std. Error	t value	Pr(> t)
(Intercept)	-0.027373	0.171182	-0.160	0.87296
partyCon/Deputy Speaker	0.063366	0.193902	0.327	0.74383
partyConservative	-0.001947	0.091025	-0.021	0.98293
partyDemocratic Unionist Party	0.002066	0.093482	0.022	0.98237
partyDep Speaker/Conservative	-0.077301	0.157614	-0.490	0.62383
partyDeputy Speaker	0.011644	0.159571	0.073	0.94183
partyGreen Party	-0.040995	0.092666	-0.442	0.65822
partyIndependent	-0.033454	0.093101	-0.359	0.71936
partyIndependent Labour	0.088199	0.203334	0.434	0.66447
partyLabour	0.014213	0.090934	0.156	0.87580
partyLabour/Deputy Speaker	0.157253	28.715693	0.005	0.99563
partyLiberal Democrat	0.017413	0.091201	0.191	0.84858
partyNon-affiliated	0.014020	0.091421	0.153	0.87812
partyPlaid Cymru	0.042244	0.092121	0.459	0.64656
partyScottish National Party	0.027046	0.091392	0.296	0.76729
partySpeaker	0.010790	0.159417	0.068	0.94604
partyUK Independence Party	0.025270	0.109384	0.231	0.81731
partyUlster Unionist	-0.004520	0.098501	-0.046	0.96340
stanceDid not vote	0.020105	0.187669	0.107	0.91469
stanceLaw Lord, probable Remain	-0.017236	0.141033	-0.122	0.90273
stanceLaw Lord, Unknown	0.256118	0.329117	0.778	0.43648
stanceLeave	0.043236	0.138736	0.312	0.75532
stanceNeutral	0.011073	0.053580	0.207	0.83629
stanceProbable Leave	0.036013	0.158381	0.227	0.82014
stanceProbable Remain	0.054806	0.139159	0.394	0.69371
stanceRemain	0.040613	0.138705	0.293	0.76968
stanceRemain/Neutral	-0.156737	28.719308	-0.005	0.99565
stanceSpeaker	0.005050	0.108393	0.047	0.96284
stanceThomas	0.176755	0.325327	0.543	0.58693
stanceUnknown	0.052966	0.138986	0.381	0.70315
stanceUnknown, although against 2nd ref	0.023439	0.142409	0.165	0.86927
genderMale	-0.020107	0.004875	-4.125	3.76e-05 ***
s(date)1	-0.046508	0.053848	-0.864	0.38779
s(date)2	0.113719	0.046652	2.438	0.01481 *
s(date)3	-0.011730	0.035192	-0.333	0.73891
s(date)4	0.054877	0.035730	1.536	0.12462
s(date)5	0.024958	0.037315	0.669	0.50362
s(date)6	0.011689	0.036352	0.322	0.74780
s(date)7	0.103902	0.035625	2.917	0.00355 **
s(date)8	-0.195471	0.064336	-3.038	0.00239 **
s(date)9	0.335527	0.226360	1.482	0.13832
s(date)10	0.167878	0.036304	4.624	3.83e-06 ***

Signif. codes: 0 '***' 0.001 '**' 0.01 '*' 0.05 '.' 0.1 ' ' 1

Topic 15:

Coefficients:

	Estimate	Std. Error	t value	Pr(> t)
(Intercept)	-0.085833	0.191384	-0.448	0.653817
partyCon/Deputy Speaker	0.044277	0.173942	0.255	0.799078
partyConservative	0.083358	0.100342	0.831	0.406151
partyDemocratic Unionist Party	0.007775	0.103099	0.075	0.939892
partyDep Speaker/Conservative	0.015065	0.172846	0.087	0.930546
partyDeputy Speaker	0.059154	0.178477	0.331	0.740325
partyGreen Party	0.037761	0.102766	0.367	0.713301
partyIndependent	0.018740	0.103088	0.182	0.855759
partyIndependent Labour	0.020527	0.173134	0.119	0.905626
partyLabour	0.059849	0.100363	0.596	0.550976
partyLabour/Deputy Speaker	-0.079215	31.327699	-0.003	0.997983
partyLiberal Democrat	0.076886	0.100667	0.764	0.445034
partyNon-affiliated	0.091697	0.100621	0.911	0.362164
partyPlaid Cymru	0.015690	0.101246	0.155	0.876852
partyScottish National Party	0.041053	0.100906	0.407	0.684134
partySpeaker	0.062627	0.178713	0.350	0.726025
partyUK Independence Party	0.041493	0.120463	0.344	0.730519
partyUlster Unionist	-0.009184	0.107281	-0.086	0.931780
stanceDid not vote	0.153121	0.255634	0.599	0.549204
stanceLaw Lord, probable Remain	0.008576	0.156902	0.055	0.956412
stanceLaw Lord, Unknown	-0.028545	0.207778	-0.137	0.890733
stanceLeave	0.069415	0.154379	0.450	0.652985
stanceNeutral	0.027498	0.059620	0.461	0.644662
stanceProbable Leave	-0.009851	0.174277	-0.057	0.954926
stanceProbable Remain	0.046412	0.154803	0.300	0.764331
stanceRemain	0.064994	0.154277	0.421	0.673562
stanceRemain/Neutral	0.182155	31.328753	0.006	0.995361
stanceSpeaker	0.012986	0.119238	0.109	0.913281
stanceThomas	-0.030014	0.208260	-0.144	0.885411
stanceUnknown	0.035175	0.154483	0.228	0.819891
stanceUnknown, although against 2nd ref	0.035669	0.159051	0.224	0.822560
genderMale	-0.006157	0.005300	-1.162	0.245395
s(date)1	0.219953	0.061950	3.550	0.000387 ***
s(date)2	-0.058105	0.053289	-1.090	0.275585
s(date)3	-0.008759	0.040266	-0.218	0.827804
s(date)4	0.084592	0.040817	2.072	0.038262 *
s(date)5	-0.022938	0.042137	-0.544	0.586217
s(date)6	0.022992	0.041150	0.559	0.576360
s(date)7	0.053584	0.039851	1.345	0.178796
s(date)8	-0.073596	0.072598	-1.014	0.310739
s(date)9	0.502679	0.252738	1.989	0.046750 *
s(date)10	-0.042651	0.040479	-1.054	0.292075

 Signif. codes: 0 '***' 0.001 '**' 0.01 '*' 0.05 '.' 0.1 ' ' 1